

found to be a bit more active than the samples activated at 973 and 1273 K. Similar observation with respect to the catalytic activity is also recorded (Table 1) in case of LaNiO_3 .

As reported in the literature⁶ the degraded products of carbamide decomposition at low temperature which occurs in two steps are biuret and ammonia. Our experimental data also support the scheme.

Fig. 1 shows the plots of volume of ammonia obtained against the time for the thermal degradation of carbamide without and with the sample of LaCoO_3 activated at 973 K. Similar plots have also been obtained in case of the samples of LaNiO_3 .

Fig. 1. Kinetics of degradation of carbamide: (1), (2), (3) urea, and (4), (5), (6) (urea + sample) at 413, 423 and 433 K respectively.

It is to be noted that all the samples activate the degradation of carbamide although their degree of activation differs. From plots (volume of ammonia vs time) the simple calculation yields 93.33, 156.66 and 223.33 mm^3 of NH_3 at 413, 423 and 433 K respectively in 10 s. However with the samples of LaNiO_3 activated at 973 K, 110.00, 176.66 and 253.33 mm^3 of NH_3 are obtained at the corresponding temperature in the same specified time from the same quantity of urea. These observations conclude that samples of perovskite type oxide containing Ni appear catalytically more active in comparison to that containing Co. This is also obvious from the rate constant data presented in Table 1.

Table 1 also contains the data on excess surface oxygen (E.S.O.) and acidity of our sample. These values decrease regularly with the rise in temperature of activation of the samples. Similar variation in the values of E.S.O. of LaCoO_3 with the rise in calcination temperature has been reported by Madhok⁶. However, from the analysis of our experimental data we conclude that the E.S.O. and

acidity seem to play no significant role towards the catalytic activity of the samples.

The plots of $\log A$ vs E_a (energy of activation) values show linear relationship. It indicates that the active centres are chiefly transition metal ion, i.e. Ni^{2+} in LaNiO_3 and Co^{2+} , Co^{3+} in LaCoO_3 . Thus, the variation in activity of the samples might be attributed to the different amount of transition metal ionic species distributed on the surface. Similar type of observation has been reported by Johnson (Jr.) *et al.*⁷ for the catalytic activity of LaMeO_3 oxide (Me = Fe, Co, Mn) for the oxidation of Co.

Thus, it is concluded that the transition metal ions are responsible for the activity of the LaMO_3 type oxides and rare earth ions moderate the catalytic activity of the transition metal ions.

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Studies on the Effect of Alkali on the Compounds related to Aminoimidazoliumcarboxamides

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1,3-Disubstituted-4-amino-5-carboxamidoimidazolium salts undergo base-catalysed Dimroth type rearrangement to produce 1-alkyl-4-substituted-aminoimidazole-5-carboxamides^{1,2}. Presence of bulky groups on imidazolium nitrogens, however, leads to a pyrazine ring formation in similar treatment reported recently³. These observations provided impetus to study the effect of the groups on N_1 and N_3 of aminoimidazolecarboxamide and its

5-Amino-4-cyano-1-diphenylmethylimidazole (1b) : To the DMF-POCl₃ complex (DMF 8 ml, POCl₃ 1.6 ml, 13 mmol) was added **1a** (2.2 g, 7.5 mmol) in one lot and the resulting solution stirred in an ice-bath for 45 min and at room temperature for 1 h. The resulting viscous mass was poured onto crushed ice (15 g) and basified with excess of aqueous ammonia. The yellow product was collected by filtration, washed well with ice-water, dried and crystallised from ethanol (1.5 g, 75%), m.p. 199–200° (Found : C, 74.37; H, 5.08; N, 20.47. C₁₇H₁₄N₄ requires : C, 74.45; H, 5.10; N, 20.43%; ν_{\max} 3 400, 3 190 (NH₂) and 2 220 cm⁻¹ (C≡N).

4-Amino-5-carboxamido-3-methyl-1-phenacylimidazolium bromide (2) : A mixture of **1c**¹ (1.4 g, 10 mmol) and phenacylbromide (2.2 g, 11 mmol) in DMF (3 ml) was refluxed for 45 min and the mixture was cooled. The resulting solid was washed well with acetone, dried and recrystallised from water (2.3 g, 68%), m.p. 249–50° (Found : C, 46.14; H, 4.30; N, 16.66. C₁₃H₁₃N₄O₂Br requires : C, 46.15; H, 4.40; N, 16.56%; ν_{\max} 3 350, 3 100 (NH₂) and 1 660 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-d₆, D₂O) 3.68 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.12 (2H, s, CH₂COPh), 7.44–7.84 (5H, m, ArH) and 8.88 (1H, s, C₅-H).

Action of alkali on 2 : A solution of **2** (0.4 g, 1.1 mmol) in 2% aqueous sodium hydroxide (4 ml, 2 mmol) was refluxed for 10 min and cooled. The resulting solid was recrystallised from water to afford **1c** (superimposable ir spectrum).

9-Diphenylmethylhypoxanthine (3) : A mixture of **1a** (0.5 g, 1.7 mmol) and formamide (6 ml) was heated in an oil-bath at 180° for 1.5 h. The mixture was then cooled to room temperature and diluted with water. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol; yield nearly quantitative, m.p. 267–68° (Found : C, 71.61; H, 4.64; N, 18.44. C₁₈H₁₄N₄O requires : C, 71.52; H, 4.63; N, 18.54%).

7-Diphenylmethylimidazo[4,5-d][1,2,3]triazine-4(3H)-one (4) : To a thoroughly cooled suspension of **1a** (1.46 g, 5 mmol) in 1 : 1 aqueous HCl (25 ml) was added a solution of sodium nitrite (0.7 g, 10 mmol) in water (8 ml) in one lot with stirring. The mixture was stirred in an ice-bath for 15 min when a clear solution was obtained. The solution was then allowed to attain room temperature when a solid began to separate. After keeping it at room temperature for 1 h, the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to afford **4** (0.75 g, 50%), m.p. 184–85° (Found : C, 67.38; H, 4.38; N, 23.20. C₁₇H₁₃N₅O requires : C, 67.32; H, 4.29; N, 23.10%).

7-Methyl-9-diphenylmethylhypoxanthinium toluene-sulphonate (5) : A mixture of **3** (1.5 g, 5 mmol) and methyl toluene-*p*-sulphonate (1 g, 5.3 mmol) in DMF (2 ml) was refluxed for 45 min. The mixture was then cooled and triturated with ethyl acetate. The resulting sticky mass was dissolved in minimum amount of methanol and kept at -5° for several days when crystals of **5** separated out (1 g, 40%),

which was recrystallised from methanol-ethyl acetate, m.p. 224–25° (Found : C, 63.83; H, 4.88; N, 11.40. C₂₈H₂₄N₄O₄S requires : C, 63.93; H, 4.91; N, 11.57%).

4-Diphenylmethylamino-5-(N-methylformylamino)-1H,6H-pyrimidine-6-one (6) : A solution of **5** (0.2 g, 0.4 mmol) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%, 2.6 ml) was heated on a steam-bath for 1 h. The mixture was then cooled and acidified with acetic acid. The formyl derivative separated out was collected by filtration, dried and crystallised from ethyl acetate, the yield being nearly quantitative, m.p. 236–37° (Found : C, 68.29; H, 5.28; N, 16.73. C₁₉H₁₈N₄O₂ requires : C, 68.26; H, 5.38; N, 16.76%).

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Synthesis of New Substituted Chloroenamines from *N*-Methyl-2-chloroacetoacetamide†

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In continuation of our earlier studies on the synthesis of new enamines from *N*-methylacetamide¹, we report herein the synthesis of the 1-chloro-2-(aryl/aralkylamino)-*N*-methylcrotonamides (Scheme 1).

R = Aryl and aralkylamines

Scheme 1

The starting compound *N*-methyl-2-chloroacetoacetamide (**1**) was obtained by the chlorination of *N*-methylacetoacetamide². A number of 1-chloro-2-(aryl/aralkylamino)-*N*-methylcrotonamides (**3**) have been prepared according to the methods described earlier¹ by reacting **1** with aryl- and aralkylamines (**2**) in dry benzene or toluene. The structures of

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